

EDUCATION POLICY DEVELOPMENT AND ITS IMPORTANCE OVERCOME INEQUALITY IN ACCESS TO EDUCATION

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Abstract

The main objective of this research is to understand and analyze descriptively related problems Inequality in access to education, so that problems can be identified and solutions can be found. The qualitative descriptive type took 50 key informants proportionally to obtain sharp and in-depth information, and supported by secondary data the results of this research indicate that special classroom programs can help students from advantaged backgrounds obtain a better education. Whereas students from disadvantaged families often do not have access to the information and resources needed to support them in their education. Special education” can be defined as the science that consists of various classes of extraordinary learners in terms of assessment, diagnosis, and the development of appropriate educational initiatives and teaching methods. Several actions that can be taken to overcome inequality in access to education, increasing awareness about stigma and discrimination, resources through the schools, teachers and supporting facilities are the same. Education has a contribution to social aspects so that it can bring changes in behavior, morals, better ethics and social and economic welfare.

Keywords: Inequality Access, Quality Education, Adequate Facilities, Appropriate Policies, Education Policy.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's basic constitution, the 1945 Constitution (UUD 45) requires the government to provide national education services and guarantee the right to receive a decent education. All people, both in urban and rural areas, from race, ethnicity, religion, and upper and lower socio-economic classes have the right to this quality education (Sartono & Herwin, 2022). In the social stratification literature, social inequality in education has been the subject of much research in recent decades. Relevant inequalities in educational opportunities - especially in secondary education - have prompted several studies to study educational transitions in more detail by paying attention to institutional aspects of

the school system that may contribute to the transmission of inequalities (Eval & Res, 2024).

Since there are still relevant inequalities in terms of access to education, especially at the higher education level, some research has begun to study educational transitions in more depth. They focus on institutional characteristics of school systems that may contribute to the spread of these inequalities. Some countries, such as the United States, have explored the role of different curricula or different curriculum pathways in secondary education (Gamoran & Mare, 2021). Accessing quality educational services is still a problem in the world of education. Schools that are considered to have good quality education are apparently unable to meet the needs of the community around the school fairly. Good quality education is a top priority for all countries in the world, according to the Sustainable Development Goals (Suryana, 2020).

Several problems are still being faced in education development in Indonesia, such as expanding and equalizing access; improving quality, relevance and competitive; structure governance, accountability public image; and increased financing (Suryana, 2020). Student raised in low-income families are affected by poverty in several ways. These include lack of study habits and home learning experiences; lack of access to a computer; poor housing; unhealthy eating patterns; possible mental health problems in the family; domestic violence; and stress associated with low salaries (Sartono & Herwin, 2022). The problem of inequality of opportunity is the most difficult for some people to get opportunities or access to a better life. To get superior students or class input, it is necessary to meet the criteria for talented or intelligent students in accordance with Decree Number 054/U/1993 from the Minister of Education and Culture (Suhartono, 2021).

Which regulates educational services for students who have high intelligence potential or special talents, educational pathways Schools must provide special class programs and programs for students who have special talents and extraordinary intelligence (Koster & Regt, 2020) Active participation of students is an important component whose characteristics must be analyzed in designing learning. Active participation of students is an important component that determines the success of achieving competency. Students are one of the important components that influence the effectiveness of learning (Irawan & Kuswanto, 2020).

Manado City as a benchmark for education in North Sulawesi Province has various challenges in equalizing access to education in all aspects. The number of schools that have the title of best school makes Manado City a destination for students from various places in North Sulawesi province and even from outside. Senior High School Binsus Manado is one of the many schools that has the title of superior school which has a number of attractions for junior high school graduates to enter this school. It is feared that the emergence of superior schools and superior classes will have a negative impact on students because there are pros and cons to the process. Of course, this is a big challenge for Senior High School Binsus Manado due to rapid changes in the curriculum.

As a government school, Senior High School Binsus Manado still has students who have difficulty getting equal access in the field of education, such as differences in the two types of classes, namely binsus classes and regular classes, differences in class facilities, teaching staff and also several other inequalities.

A very popular education reform strategy among policymakers around the world is school-based management. In various countries, definitions of school-based management differ, mainly based on program characteristics and objectives (Afifah, 2017). Influenced by culture and the program itself, and the political and cultural context. In the case of shared decision making, parents and other stakeholders are involved in the process (Muspiroh, 2016).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social capital first appeared in Lyda Judson Hanifan's discussion of rural school community centers in 1920. The real substances that explain people's daily lives were called "social capital. Hanifan mainly focused on increasing good will, friendship, sympathy, and social relationships that form social units (Gannon & Roberts. 2020). The use of social capital theory as mentioned makes social capital the center of research and policy discussions. James Coleman created the concept of social capital based on the research results of Coleman, 1990 and was followed by Francis Fukuyama 1995. , and Pierre Bourdieu emphasizes theoretical understanding (Arezzo, 2017). Social capital, according to Pierre Bourdieu, is the amount of resources, both actual and virtual, that are accumulated in an individual or group due to having a long-term network consisting of somewhat institutionalized relationships of acquaintance and recognition (McCarthy & Pitt, 2019).

James Coleman said social capital is the ability of people to work together to achieve common goals in various groups and organizations. Robert D. Putnam said social capital is elements of social life such as networks, norms and trust that encourage people to act together more effectively to achieve common goals (Syahril, 2022). In recent years, James Coleman, who has brought the term "social capital" into wider use, has argued that social capital is a public good, and therefore would be less created by private agents interacting in markets. This is clearly wrong because almost everyone needs cooperation to achieve their goals, it makes sense that they produce it as a personal product (Kalar & Antoncic, 2016). Social capital is part of an organized society, which is seen from the network of work, norms and values of trust that encourage cooperation and beneficial actions. In particular, he believed that the destruction of family and community ties would have a major impact on social life (Gannon & Roberts. 2020).

Loss of strong social ties is usually caused by lower trust scores. also social capital that is formed from small populations to large populations. Economic and political health is strongly influenced by the strength of this social capital (Robertson & Pitt, 2019). Middle school students' social social capital should be measured in various contexts as well as students' social capital at home, as shown in the following Figure 1.

According to a number of studies, family and school social capital still has an influence even after the existence of human capital. Additionally, the financial impact on families and schools remains. However, it is unclear to what extent additional resources can serve as a substitute for social capital (Anwar & Elfiah, 2019). For example, if modeling the indirect effect of family socioeconomic status through family social capital, the direct effect of family social capital on test scores is not significant, then it can be concluded that we should emphasize the indirect effect of family socioeconomic status on test scores (Muspiroh, 2016). Social capital definitely exists at home and also at school. The homes parents build for children and the school environments children experience can be distinguished by safety, intellectual stimulation, and affective support. The concept of resource dilution emerged as a result of the number of students per teacher or counselor and larger family sizes (Dewi, 2019). Children who attend private schools have higher social closure compared to children who attend public schools due to similarities in norms, including norms of social behavior (Syahril, 2022). Parents who do not know the whereabouts of their children and friends are socially closed. Children affiliated with important institutions such as churches or other private institutions should receive the same benefits. In addition, human resources exist at home and at school (Ngurah Suragangga, 2017).

Parents may be highly or poorly educated or have more or less mental abilities. Likewise, teachers have varying skill levels; This human capital can be used by adults to encourage good social behavior. Finally, there are stronger or weaker resources that can be used to improve children's social well-being—both at home and at school—with financial resources (Nurlailiyah, 2019). They focused on the productive and collegial interaction of all stakeholders and argued that the conceptualisation of distributed leadership is not just about the actions of individual leaders but rather about interactions among leaders, followers and the situation. Distributed leadership can be conceptualised as a collective, situated and distributed practice, not equivalent to a teacher's behaviour or a function of

her/his knowledge and skill, but rather consisting of interactions between teachers and students related to intellectual material and aspects of the situation (Jingping Sun, 2023). At the same time, the combination of resources at home and at school can also have an impact. The existence of shared values can make someone want to be part of the network. Mostly, a person chooses to invest in a network because it helps them live better (investing in friendship), having the economic value of joining a union (Cardno, 2019; Ward, 2021). If social capital is lost, the unity of society will be threatened, or at least collective problems will become difficult to solve. The stronger the social capital, the stronger the resilience, fighting power and quality of life of the community, because togetherness helps reduce burdens and share thoughts. Without social capital, society is very easily disturbed or destroyed by other people (Kalar & Antoncic, 2016).

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a qualitative approach, emphasizing meaning, reasoning, definition of a particular situation in a particular context, researching more things related to everyday life. Therefore, the sequence of activities can change depending on the conditions and the number of symptoms found (Sugiyono, 2016). The research collected primary data through an open but structured interview process with get interview guidelines. Key informants in this research are grouped into three, namely direct informants, indirect informants and informants who are related to the research objectives (Suharsimi, 2010). The focus of this research consists of; a). Inequality of facilities, b) Qualifications of teachers who teach, and c) Quality of Materials. The data analysis process in this research adopts the thinking of Miles and Hubberman (2014), which basically includes four activity flows after the data collection process, namely: data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing, as presented in Figure 1 interactive model.

Figure 2: Components of data analysis Interactive

Source: Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014)

Data collection, all collected through methods that have been used in research, for example observation, interviews, documentation or literature study to then be processed for the next activity. Data reduction, namely the process of selecting, focusing attention and simplifying, abstracting and transforming rough data that emerges from written notes from the field (Moleong, 2010). Data display, the presentation of this data as much as possible presents data or information arranged in such a way that making it easier to analyze, drawing conclusions, qualitative research is expected to be new findings that have never existed before, it can be in the form of a description or picture of an object that was previously dim or dark and becomes clear after being researched, the findings are in the form of a causal or interactive relationship.

RESULTS

This Specially Assisted High School was established as a realization of the results of the 1993 Ministry of Education and Culture National Working Meeting in Jakarta. When the Special Education High School was established on September 22 1993, the Principal was Drs. J.C Namsa, who at that time also served as Principal of SMA Negeri Manado. This was because the Special Development High School (Special Development Class), at that time was placed at SMA Negeri Manado. A year later, the Special Assistance High School was transferred to Manado State High School 1 and at that time the Principal of State High School 1 and at the same time the Special Assistance High School was Mr. Ferry Makalew, BSc.

In 1995, Mr. Ferry Makalew ended his term as Principal of Manado State High School 1 which also included Manado Special Development High School 1. He was replaced by the Principal of SMA Negeri 7, namely Mr. Drs. J.C Namsa. So SMA Negeri 1 Special Guidance Manado became SMA (General High School) Negeri 1 Special Guidance Manado under the leadership of the Principal, Mr Drs. J.C. Namsa. In the implementation of the Manado Special Development High School which is now located in the Kleak Ward I Subdistrict, curriculum matters are handled directly by Manado State High School 1 and the provision of facilities, infrastructure and dormitory programs is handled by Manado State High School 8 (now Manado State High School 9). This situation is understandable because the Special Guidance High School is located in Kleak adjacent to Manado State High School 9. In the 1998/1999 school year the Special Guidance High School was fully handled by Manado State 9 High School, with the Principal Dra. Margaretha Assa.

Now Binsus High School is a superior class with students who have high abilities from Manado State High School 9, so it is often called Manado State High School 9 Binsus because all administration is handled by Manado State High School 9. Even so, Senior High School Binsus still has a lot of achievements and competencies to be proud of. Unequal access to education among students is a complex issue that has a significant impact on educational equality. A student's opportunity to obtain a high-quality education can be influenced by a number of factors, including economic circumstances, geographic location, social, cultural, and political circumstances. UNESCO conducted research

showing that inadequate access to education remains a significant problem in many countries, especially for vulnerable groups such as women, children from poor families, children with disabilities, and ethnic minorities. To achieve equality in learning for students from groups who experience difficulties in access to education, there are often complex problems. For example, data from UNESCO's 2020 Global Education Report shows that worldwide around 258 million children and young people do not receive formal education, and the majority of them come from poor families. The findings sourced from informants during primary data collection can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Inequality of Facilities, Teacher Qualifications and Material Quality

No	Class Binsus	Class Reguler	Coding
1	Our class is very comfortable because several facilities such as air conditioning and better desks	Even though there is no air conditioning in the classroom, we still study as usual	Facilities Inequality
2	In our class there is an LCD and our teachers often teach using the LCD	Most of our teachers still use markers and white boards to teach us, very rarely use LCDs	
3	Almost all of the classrooms are permanent and must be maintained by all students in the class	Our classroom is an old classroom and has some damage to the inside and outside of the classroom	
4	Most of our teachers are senior teachers who are experienced in their respective fields	Just like teachers in other schools, there are honorary teachers and also ASN	Qualifications of teachers who teach
5	Almost all teachers teach using laptops and facilities such as LCDs	I usually teach using the facilities in the classroom, such as a blackboard, sometimes even under my own laptop.	
6	Many of our teachers have Master's degrees	The title doesn't matter for us as students studying, but what is important is going to class because sometimes there are teachers who don't come and are replaced by honorary teachers.	
7	Usually we study until the afternoon, the others have gone home while we haven't if the material hasn't been finished yet.	We come home from school according to schedule, when the bell rings we go straight home	Material Quality
8	There are teachers who provide additional hours of lessons if there is still time, or there is material that is left behind	Sometimes if there is material that is not finished, it is given as an assignment and completed at home	
9	Still taking part in extracurricular activities, but the material must be an obligation, so sometimes you have to remedial if the material is not finished yet.	There is an exception if taking part in a competition does not require taking part in class lessons	

Soerce(s): Own ealboration

Equal opportunities for all students at Senior High School Binsus Manado has not yet become a reality felt by all parties. The process of admitting new students and dividing class groups creates inequality of access between students at the same school. Students who have better capital will certainly get a room that has better learning support facilities compared to other students.

Many criticisms have been leveled by academics and educational practitioners regarding the quality of education in Indonesia; one of the main problems is unequal education. Indonesian education should meet the needs of a broad, growing and diverse population that has differences in participation levels between regions. Indonesia as a country consists of a diverse spectrum of society.

Much of the learning literature is concerned with acquiring knowledge, skills, or roles in various institutional settings, such as schools or workplaces. This makes it possible to differentiate between different learning contexts and conditions.

The curriculum plays an important role as a guide for teaching and learning at all levels of education in an effort to improve the quality of education. The curriculum reflects the goals, principles, and social expectations of education in addition to serving as a foundation for teaching subject matter (Suryana, 2020).

However, in reality, various difficulties often prevent educational goals from being achieved. In practice, the Merdeka curriculum, which has become the curriculum applied at all levels throughout Indonesia, is still not as expected by the government (Suhartono, 2021).

This also happened at Senior High School Binsus Manado, where there were still gaps which made implementation hampered by the differences between specially trained classes and regular classes. The main aim of the independent curriculum is to produce the next generation who are intelligent, characterized and talented and prepare students for a future full of opportunities and difficulties, in addition to improving the standard of education [30].

Based on the results of research in the field, it turns out that students at Senior High School Binsus Manado still do not have equal access to the implementation of the independent curriculum where teaching staff are still divided between specially developed classes and regular classes so that material achievement will definitely have an impact on each student.

The independent curriculum, which will be implemented in 2022 after the Covid_19 pandemic, is a solution for students in schools that are more focused on independent learning. This curriculum is not something new but rather an improvement on the previous curriculum, but it still has obstacles like other curricula.

This research supports and develops research from Suryana (2020); Suhartono (2021) and Syahril (2022) that various challenges cannot be separated from curriculum changes in schools from elementary to tertiary level.

Various breakthroughs have been made in various regions to improve the quality of education so that it is evenly distributed throughout Indonesia but this has not been realized to date due to various obstacles such as regional conditions, human resources, technology and a number of other obstacles. Freedom of learning and the Pancasila student profile are the basis for the development of the current independence curriculum, but it turns out that it is not in line with curriculum practice in the field where there are still limited access that cannot be reached by all students in the same school to realize freedom of learning.

An independent curriculum gives schools more freedom to design their own learning, but this can actually widen educational differences between schools with sufficient resources and schools that do not, even between students in the same school with a class system. The government must ensure that all schools have the necessary facilities to support the independent curriculum, teachers and schools must be properly trained to implement the independent curriculum.

Parents must also be involved in their children's learning process and understand the independent curriculum, but all these things cannot be implemented at Senior High School Binsus Manado. Existing studies on the relationship between schooling and social capital have largely focused on this concept, Figure 3.

The results obtained are in line with theory and studies by Kalar & Antoncic (2016), Robertson & Pitt (2019), Gannon & Roberts (2020) and Eval & Res (2024), that many efforts have been made to adapt the curriculum to the needs of students and society, failures in curriculum implementation still occur frequently.

Some of the causes of this failure include incompatibility with real world developments, lack of teacher readiness to implement the new curriculum, and administrative and logistical obstacles in providing the necessary resources. By understanding the components that cause this failure, we can determine what actions can be taken to improve curriculum implementation and increase overall educational effectiveness.

Seeing these conditions, only a few studies have directly investigated bridging social capital accessed through school ties. Access to social capital through school ties is primarily inferred from the relationship between social capital and education (Gannon & Roberts, 2020).

Furthermore, stated that schools are important social organizations where social capital can be accumulated through social ties formed intentionally or unintentionally (Arezzo, 2017). Social capital as an attribute that emerges from a social network consisting of relationships such as trust and reciprocity.

Figure 3: Recommendations from research results

Source(s): Own elaboration

Curriculum is a plan created to help students learn, schools or educational institutions and their teachers are responsible for implementing it. So, the government, educational institutions and society must work together well to implement the curriculum. The process of equalizing education begins with the implementation of the curriculum and improving the quality at every level of education (Afifah, 2017). This quality improvement is aimed at improving the quality of input and graduates, processes, teachers, facilities and infrastructure, and the budget used for education. Even though the learning curriculum has become more sophisticated, its accuracy has not been felt by all students. Even in the same school there are still students who receive different teaching, as is the case at Senior High School Binsus Manado.

There are classes that have facilities that support the implementation of the independent curriculum but a number of other classes do not. Likewise, if an educational unit does not receive the support of an effective communication network and collaboration with relevant stakeholders, curriculum implementation will not run well or may even encounter obstacles (Dewi, 2019). Schools must support communication networks and partnerships to strengthen the implementation of an independent curriculum through the synergy of mutual cooperation, sharing inspiration, and supporting the realization of beneficial learning for students.

Curriculum failure can come from the absence of teachers in its implementation. Teachers should function as a motor and inspiration for the success of various independent learning programs, such as differentiated learning, projects to increase the profile of Pancasila students, assessments, and the use of technology to support learning (Suryana, 2020). As a result, strengthening the presence of teachers through the necessary development programs must be carried out consistently and continuously. This is especially important considering that the results of teacher professional development programs so far have not had a significant influence on improving the quality of life in Indonesia (Suhartono, 2021). An inseparable inequality in the implementation of the curriculum in schools is that every subject teacher must obtain digital technology, especially in terms of searching and using various learning resources, in accordance with the direction of the learning process in the technology-based independent curriculum.

This suggests that both now and in the future, teachers will need to be adept at using digital technology to help students learn. In situations like this, teachers must immediately begin to recognize and utilize various learning platforms, including email, hybrid learning, e-learning, digital-based resources, and digital-based learning media (Irawan & Kuswanto, 2020). With these efforts, learning can become more interesting, interactive and contextual, and allow for the development of more in-depth material as needed. Students are trained to utilize technology positively, adaptively and innovatively towards technological advances through empowering digital-based learning. The difference between specially developed classes and regular classes creates unequal access between students at the same school. Students in regular classes do not have the opportunity to learn in an environment that is as competitive as that of a binsus class, and they also do not have access to the in-depth and challenging curriculum that is available in a binsus class. As a result, students who study in regular classes or regular classes do not have the opportunity to be educated by teachers who are as experienced as binsus class teachers.

CONCLUSION

When compared with students in urban areas, students in rural and remote areas have less access to high-quality schools, experienced teachers, and adequate educational infrastructure. Compared with students from rich families, students from poor families are more likely to drop out of school, be late for school, and not have access to adequate educational resources. Boys and girls have wider access to education in some countries. Students with disabilities often face difficulties obtaining an inclusive, high-quality education.

The government must create and implement fair and inclusive education policies to address disparities between teaching facilities and infrastructure and teacher qualifications, because high-quality teachers can improve student achievement. The government can do several things to overcome inequality in the quality of education, such as increasing the education budget, allocating a larger budget for education to improve

facilities and infrastructure, and increasing teacher capabilities. In addition, the government must implement fair and inclusive education policies that ensure that every student has access to a diverse education.

In this research, there are several limitations. For example, there is little research on inequality of access to education in top class programs. As a result, it is difficult to generalize the results of this study. Most research concentrates on one aspect of inequality, such as inequality in economic terms or academic achievement. It is rare for research to examine inequality from various elements comprehensively. It is still difficult to obtain data on inequality in access to education and superior class programs. This makes research on this topic more difficult.

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